

The removal of hydrogen sulfide from biogas by water absorption combined with iron oxide (Fe₂O₃)

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Abstract

The removal of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) from biogas is necessary due to the H₂S having corrosive properties to ensure safe biogas utilization. Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) sorbents are extensively studied for H₂S removal due to their easy operation and low operating cost. This study aimed to measure the efficiency of H₂S removal from biogas by the technique of water absorption combined with Fe₂O₃ chemical adsorption. The biogas flow rate of 1 l/min with an H₂S concentration of 3,000–3,200 ppm was monitored for the experimental time of 60 min. The experiments were tested by varying 100–300 ml water absorbent, 10–40 g Fe₂O₃, and combining 100–300 ml water with 25 g Fe₂O₃. It was found that the volume of water and Fe₂O₃ had significant effects on H₂S removal from biogas. The combination of 300 ml of water and 25 g of Fe₂O₃ has shown promising results, with the highest H₂S removal efficiency of 84.8%. This system offered exceptional techniques of absorption combined with chemical adsorption capacity and, therefore, capable of upgrading biogas to biomethane.

Keywords: Biogas, Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃), Absorption, Adsorption

1. Introduction

Biogas produced by anaerobic digestion is a clean and environmentally friendly alternative to fossil fuels. It contains about 55–65% methane (CH_4) and other constituents, including 30–40% carbon dioxide (CO_2), fractions of water vapor, and trace amounts of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) [1]. Biogas production helps in waste management by utilizing organic waste, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and promoting sustainable energy practices. H_2S in biogas, typically ranging from 1,000 to 30,000 ppm, occurred during the microbial breakdown of organic matter, making it a relevant consideration for biogas utilization [2, 3, 4]. H_2S is highly undesirable in energy transformation because it can be reverted into highly corrosive and environmentally hazardous sulfur dioxide (SO_2) and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4). Hydrogen sulfide removal is essential for any eventual utilization of biogas [5, 6, 7]. Fe_2O_3 was used for biogas purification in packed column reactors and had H_2S removal efficiency. It is typically used with other H_2S removal techniques to achieve optimal results and ensure the overall quality of the biogas [8]. Water absorption has been generally used to remove H_2S [9]. To improve the H_2S removal efficiency, water absorption combined with Fe_2O_3 is another choice as a straightforward, practical, low-cost method that solves problems for the end users of biogas technology. This research studied the H_2S removal from biogas by water absorption combined with Fe_2O_3 chemical adsorption in a packed column system. The quantities of water absorbent and Fe_2O_3 added in the column were determined for H_2S removal efficiency.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Biogas

The study was carried out at an agricultural farm in Hatyai, Songkla, Thailand, using biogas from a fermentation dome with a capacity of 750 l/day. Biogas from pig manure and food waste were fermented in the dome digester at 35°C for 20 days of hydraulic retention time (HRT). Biogas 1 m³/day, containing hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) around 3,200 ppm, was analyzed using the Determination of H_2S Content of Fuel Gas Streams in Petroleum Refineries method [10].

2.2 Adsorbent Preparation

Iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) SCM440 type from industrial lathe waste, with a size of 0.3–0.5 cm and a length of 5–10 cm, was utilized as an adsorbent in the H_2S adsorption system. Firstly, the Fe_2O_3 was treated by immersing it in deionized water at a ratio of 2:1 (water to adsorbent) at ambient temperature for 8 hours. Then, the treated Fe_2O_3 was left to sundry under ambient temperature for 7 days to react iron with oxygen and water to form iron (III) oxide (Fe_2O_3), known as hematite.

2.3 H_2S removal system

In this experiment, H_2S removal from biogas was achieved by using the packed column. Fig. 1. shows a schematic diagram of the H_2S removal system, which mainly consisted of an acrylic column with a diameter of 5.6 cm and a height of 30 cm. The bottom of the column was filled with 100–300 ml of water and 10–50 g of treated Fe_2O_3 adsorbent. Inside the column was a small pipeline for feeding biogas from top to bottom, and a pipe tip had immersed to bubble in the water reservoir. The biogas continuously flowed up, passed through the Fe_2O_3 , and exited at the top of the column. Rotameters were equipped to measure the volumetric flow rate of inlet and outlet biogases.

Fig.1 H₂S adsorption system

Experiments were conducted to find the efficiency of H₂S removal from biogas using a packed column as calculated by Eq. (1). The biogas was constantly controlled at one l/min and measured for inlet and outlet H₂S concentration every 20 min during the experimental time for 60 min. An inlet H₂S concentration in the produced biogas was maintained at 3,000–3,200 ppm. The Determination of H₂S Content of Fuel Gas Streams in Petroleum Refineries method analyzed the H₂S concentrations. The H₂S concentration was measured by an air sampling pump and a series of impingers containing a solution of cadmium sulfate (CdSO₄) by iodometric method [11].

$$\text{H}_2\text{S removal efficiency} = \frac{\text{H}_2\text{S}_{\text{inlet}} - \text{H}_2\text{S}_{\text{outlet}}}{\text{H}_2\text{S}_{\text{inlet}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where $\text{H}_2\text{S}_{\text{inlet}}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{S}_{\text{outlet}}$ is inlet and outlet H₂S concentration, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Results of H₂S removal from biogas

The experiments of H₂S removal from biogas were performed by using water absorption, Fe₂O₃ chemical adsorption, and combining water absorption with Fe₂O₃ adsorption in a packed column system. The biogas flow rate was kept at a constant 1 l/min for all the experiments. The result of these experiments can be shown in Fig. 2. Using 300 ml water absorbent got very low H₂S removal efficiency by decreasing from 48.4 to 21.3% with time. Also, for the use of 25 g of Fe₂O₃, the efficiency decreased from 87.6 to 52.7%. The highest H₂S removal efficiency of 92.9% was achieved using Fe₂O₃ at 25 g combined with water at 300 ml and decreased to 76.9% after 60 min.

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Fig.2 Effect of comparison of the H₂S removal efficiency by water absorbent, Fe₂O₃, and combining water with Fe₂O₃

3.2 Water absorption for H₂S removal from biogas

To show the result of H₂S removal from biogas by absorption, water quantity of 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300 mL was added to the column, and bubbling 1 l/min biogas into the water. It was found that H₂S removal efficiency slightly increases with increasing water volume, as presented in Fig. 3. The highest removal efficiency of 34.4% was obtained with 300 ml of water. These results were consistent with the study reported by Horikawa et al., [9] in which the removal of H₂S in distilled water was about 20% for a biogas flow rate of 1 l/min.

Fig.3 Effect of water quantity on H₂S removal from biogas

3.3 Iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) adsorption for H_2S removal from biogas

The results of H_2S removal by Fe_2O_3 adsorbent were investigated in the adsorption column, as shown in Fig. 4. The experimental tests were all carried out using a biogas flow rate of 1 l/min for 60 min. H_2S removal efficiency from 49.4% to 76.9% by Fe_2O_3 , increasing the quantity of Fe_2O_3 adsorbent. These suggested that using Fe_2O_3 had higher H_2S removal efficiency than using the water-absorbent technique and confirmed a decrease in H_2S outlet concentration by Fe_2O_3 increasing, as reported by David Marín et al. [12].

Fig.4 Effect of iron oxide quantity on H_2S removal from biogas

3.4 Water and iron oxide combined for H_2S removal

The H_2S removal by combining water absorption and Fe_2O_3 adsorption was conducted at 25 g Fe_2O_3 with varying water of 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300 ml. The biogas flow rate was kept at a constant 1 l/min for all the experiments. The highest H_2S removal efficiency of 84.8% was obtained at Fe_2O_3 25 g and water of 300 ml. Then, the combining technique was more effectively performed for H_2S removal than adsorption or absorption alone. According to Sisani et al. [13], this system was capable of upgrading biogas to biomethane.

Fig.5 Effect of water and iron oxide quantity on H₂S removal from biogas

4. Conclusions

This work demonstrated the removal of H₂S for biogas upgrading by combining the techniques of water absorption and Fe₂O₃ adsorption. The highest H₂S removal efficiency of 85% was achieved by applying 25 g Fe₂O₃ and 300 ml water in a packed column with a biogas flow rate of 1 l/min. The discovery revealed that increasing the water content and Fe₂O₃ in the absorption system enhanced H₂S absorption. The method proposed here for upgrading biogas has promised a technique to maximize energy efficiency and reduce environmental impact and cost.

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